

Flame synthesis of nanophosphors using sub-micron aerosols

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Abstract

A flame synthesis approach is described for producing metal oxide nanoparticles. It is based on a novel microjet atomisation technique, which generates solution aerosol droplets in the sub-micron range with a mean diameter of 200 nm. Here, luminescent Eu-doped Y_2O_3 nanophosphors are successfully synthesised from aqueous metal nitrate precursors delivered to non-premixed $\text{CH}_4/\text{N}_2\text{-O}_2$ flames. The effect of droplet size and synthesis temperature on the particle formation route is experimentally investigated by comparison with micron-size droplets (mean diameter 3.5 μm) produced by ultrasonic atomisation. Depending on the synthesis temperature, the results show that particles are formed via two different mechanisms: gas-to-particle and droplet-to-particle. Using sub-micron droplets at low temperatures (1150 K), the latter mechanism allows production of luminescent $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ nanoparticles in the cubic phase, with straightforward particle size control from 10 to 100 nm by adjusting the precursor concentration in the 0.01-1 mol/L range. At higher flame temperatures (2750 K), results show that nanoparticles are formed via the gas-to-particle mechanism and have a size of 4-5 nm. In comparison with micron-size droplets, specific surface area measurements of the product powders show that sub-micron droplets form an increased fraction of nanoparticles via the gas-to-particle route. The greater developed surface area of sub-micron droplets enhances vaporisation of metal precursor molecules into the gas phase. Timescale analysis shows that the relative rates of solvent evaporation and bulk solute diffusion are also dependent on the droplet size. Electron microscopy confirms that dense particles are formed from sub-micron droplets subjected to a rapid rate of temperature increase in the flame ($\sim 10^4$ K/s). For the same synthesis conditions, micron-size droplets tend to form hollow particles, indicating that high peak temperatures near the product melting point (>2700 K) are subsequently required to promote dense particle formation.

1. Introduction

Flame synthesis can produce metal oxide nanoparticles with applications as diverse as batteries, solar cells, catalysts, materials for cosmetics, paints and inks, optical fibres, displays and lighting, medical diagnosis and treatment technologies, and remote optical sensing. The particle size is a key factor in the functionality of the material, affecting its mechanical, electrical, thermal and optical properties. In many cases, it is necessary to produce homogeneous, non-aggregated, sub-100 nm nanoparticles, with flexible control of the composition, i.e. the purity, uniformity or nanotailored structure, and the size distribution and morphology. Flames also provide a high-temperature environment suitable for producing crystalline product [1], particularly relevant for efficient luminescent materials used for displays and biomedical tracers [2], and sensors for, e.g. temperature [3]. For instance, europium-doped Y_2O_3 is an important red-emitting phosphor that has been previously synthesised in spray flames [4-6], spray drying reactors [7], and in non-premixed flames [8-12]. Such liquid-fed flame synthesis processes are especially attractive due to the high yield and use of readily-available, low-cost precursors [1, 13], often metal salts, e.g. nitrates, acetates, and chlorides.

There are two key challenges in liquid-fed flame synthesis. The first is related to the aerosol generation process, which requires efficient methods for fine droplet generation. Many methods have been developed, such as ultrasonic atomisers, two-fluid nozzles, electrosprays and rotating atomisers [14]. An important parameter is the droplet size distribution. When the aerosol is generated separately and delivered to the flame, the size of the final nanoparticle can be directly controlled by the droplet size and concentration of the metal precursor in the solvent liquid, via the *droplet-to-particle* formation mechanism. However, the atomisation techniques mentioned above typically produce aerosols with droplets a few microns in size (or larger) [15]. As such, it is difficult to synthesise product nanocrystals efficiently in the desirable size range 10-100 nm using these aerosol generation methods, unless extraordinarily dilute precursor concentrations are used [5, 16, 17].

The second challenge is to understand the particle formation mechanisms to control the nanoparticle size distribution. For flame spray pyrolysis, where the solvent is a fuel that provides the primary energy content for the flame, research efforts are directed towards identifying criteria such as the solvent composition [18], droplet size distribution [19], and the role of droplet micro-explosions [20], which ensure the formation of dense and homogeneous nanopowders via nucleation and growth from the gas-phase: the *gas-to-particle* formation route. One aim is to avoid the synthesis of hollow particles, or strongly bimodal particle size distributions caused by

the previously mentioned droplet-to-particle formation mechanism that can occur simultaneously. If on the other hand the synthesis process actually targets the particle formation from single droplets, similar problems arise. For example, regarding the aforementioned $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ phosphor, there are reports of the gas-phase formation of particles in propane- O_2 flames [8] and in a low-pressure spray pyrolysis reactor [7], and also hollow particles in H_2 -air flames [12]. However, an in-depth examination of how the droplet size and flame temperature affects the particle formation route has not been conducted.

To address these two challenges, in this study firstly we introduce a novel microjet aerosol generation method which produces sub-micron droplets, and use it to directly synthesise nanoparticles with a size below 100 nm in non-premixed flames. $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ phosphors are produced here as a platform to probe the luminescence and crystalline properties of the nanoparticles. Secondly, we examine the mechanisms of nanoparticle formation by comparison with a conventional ultrasonic atomisation process producing micron-size droplets. Specifically, the influence of flame temperature and the enhanced surface area of the sub-micron aerosol on particle formation from the gas-phase is experimentally evaluated. Particle formation mechanisms are proposed, based on analysis of the solvent evaporation/solute diffusion timescales at different droplet sizes and synthesis temperatures. Additionally, we determine the effect of droplet size and flame temperature on the formation of dense or hollow nanoparticles.

2. Experimental methods

The microjet atomiser [21, 22] (Fig. 1a) consists of a Norprene tube punctured at 2 mm intervals in rows along the top and bottom of the tube and partially submerged in the solution containing the precursor. The tube is pressurised by atomising gas (for reference, 1.75 bar gauge at 2 standard litres/minute (SLPM) N_2) that emanates from the holes, generating bubbles from the bottom rows; the bubbles rise to the liquid surface to form liquid films. Simultaneously, gas microjets from the top rows of holes interact with and burst the thin films to produce a fine aerosol that is transported to the flame. For this atomiser, the droplet load was approximately 0.1 g liquid per standard litre of gas supplied (g/L).

Fig.1 Experimental setup: atomiser sketches (a,b), synthesis burner (c), and flame photographs (d,e).

To understand the effect of droplet size on nanoparticle formation, for comparison a commercial ultrasonic atomiser (Mist maker DK-10, operating at 1.7 MHz) was used (Fig. 1b). Carrier gas entered and transported the droplets from the atomiser to the flame at a comparable load of 0.1 g/L. The droplet size distributions were characterised at the burner nozzle using a laser diffraction-based Malvern Spraytec device. Based on repeat samples measured without the flame, the error in the mean droplet size was $\pm 15\%$. The humidity of the droplet flow was measured using a hygrometer (5100-140, Electro-Tech Systems). Precursor solutions were prepared by dissolving yttrium and europium nitrates $(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Sigma-Aldrich) in deionised water with 15 mol% doping concentration (Eu substitution for Y). Metal nitrates were chosen since they are cheap and readily available, and more easily oxidised in flames due to the weak N-O bonds compared with other metal salts e.g. chlorides.

The burner (Fig. 1c) consisted of three concentric stainless steel tubes. The central tube, 10 mm in diameter, fed the precursor droplets and N_2/CH_4 carrier/atomising gases into the flame, and the inner and outer annuli contained CH_4 and O_2 gases respectively. For all experiments the O_2 and coflow air flow rates were kept constant at 4 and 10 SLPM, respectively, while the fuel flow rate was varied to change the synthesis temperature. Flow

rates were controlled using mass flow controllers and were calibrated to within 2% accuracy using a flow meter (Drycal DC-2). Depending on the flame structure, the synthesis temperatures were either approximated using the adiabatic flame temperature, or measured using a type K thermocouple positioned vertically in the flame and corrected for radiation heat loss and conduction. Throughout, the temperature error is ± 50 K.

Particles were collected on an aluminium foil 50 cm downstream using an electrostatic precipitator. The rear surface of the foil was cooled with air to ensure no sintering of the particles at the point of collection. At the same location, particles were also collected directly onto carbon-coated TEM grids.

The particles were imaged using scanning (Verios 460, FEI) and transmission (Talos F200X, FEI) electron microscopy (SEM/TEM). TEM images of at least 100 particles/sample were used for particle sizing, with size uncertainty of $\pm 20\%$ established from repeat experiments and different image magnifications. A fluorescence spectrometer (FLS980, Edinburgh Instruments) was used for luminescence characterisation of the particles. For comparison, spectra of commercial $4.9 \mu\text{m}$ $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ powder (LPRD-1 Stanford Materials Corp.) produced using a solid-state reaction were also recorded. Powder specific surface area was measured using N_2 adsorption and Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) theory (Gemini V, Micromeritics), with repeat measurements yielding $\pm 20\%$ variation.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Atomisation & droplet size distribution

Figure 2 compares the number distribution of water droplets for our microjet atomiser and the ultrasound device, for fixed conditions of 2 SLPM atomising/carrier N_2 gas. The vast fraction of droplets produced using the microjet atomiser are sub-micron in size, by number, with a mean droplet diameter of 220 nm. Comparing with ultrasonic atomisation, the mean droplet size is $3.5 \mu\text{m}$, corresponding to a factor greater than ten difference in the droplet diameter between the two atomisation approaches.

Fig. 2 Water droplet size distributions for microjet and ultrasonic atomisers.

3.2 Nanoparticle size distribution and correlation with precursor concentration

A non-premixed flame (Fig. 1d) with a closed flame front was established using 1.5 SLPM N₂/0.6 SLPM CH₄ with precursor droplets in the central tube and a small 0.15 SLPM CH₄ flow through the inner annulus. The adiabatic flame temperature was estimated to be 2750 K. Figure 3 shows an SEM image of particles produced using sub-micron droplets in this flame using a 1 mol/L precursor concentration. The particles are below 10 nm in size and appear loosely aggregated, forming connected fractal-like structures of individual crystals as evidenced by the singly-orientated crystal planes (see Fig. 3 inset).

Fig. 3 SEM image of Y₂O₃:Eu³⁺ nanoparticles produced using sub-micron 1 mol/L solution droplets at a flame temperature T=2750 K, with TEM inset.

Table 1 shows primary particle sizes for precursor concentrations 0.01-1 mol/L. The mean particle size is about 3-6 nm, and there is only a very weak dependence of the particle size on precursor concentration. This is contrary to the situation where one droplet forms one particle, i.e. following the sequence of processes of solvent

evaporation, precursor precipitation, and reactions to crystalline oxide product. Using droplet-size measurements, we verified that the mean droplet size does not change significantly between pure water (220 nm) and 0.1 mol/L solution (250 nm). Therefore the product particle mass should increase linearly with the precursor concentration (C_M), such that the particle diameter follows ($C_M^{1/3}$). Furthermore, the particle size is substantially smaller than a calculation based on the mass contained in a single droplet. Using the mean droplet diameter, the precursor concentration, and the molar volume of Y_2O_3 ($48.9 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$), it would be expected that a spherical product particle would have a diameter of 16 nm at 0.01 mol/L (increasing to 73 nm for 1 mol/L). These facts point to the conclusion that the formation route for the nanoparticles is via the gas-phase, instead of droplet-to-particle.

Table 1

Measured mean particle sizes for precursor concentrations 0.01-1 mol/L at $T=2750 \text{ K}$.

Precursor concentration (mol/L)	Mean primary particle size (nm)
0.01	3.8
0.1	3.7
1	5.6

The synthesis temperature was then reduced by passing CH_4 through the inner annulus at a flow rate of 0.35 SLPM to form an annular flame (see Fig. 1e). 1.5 SLPM N_2 carried the precursor droplets through the central tube into the high-temperature region. The peak gas temperature was 1150 K. Figure 4 shows TEM images of the nanoparticles synthesised using precursor concentrations of 0.01, 0.1 and 1 mol/L. The particles are near-spherical and non-aggregated. The internal structure is dense and polycrystalline (see inset). For these low-temperature synthesis conditions, few particles with a size consistent with formation from the gas phase are visible for the 0.01 and 0.1 mol/L concentrations, though some are apparent at 1 mol/L.

Fig. 4 TEM images of $Y_2O_3:Eu^{3+}$ nanoparticles produced using sub-micron droplets in a lower temperature flame $T=1150 \text{ K}$.

To confirm the origin of these particles, the particle size distribution as measured from TEM images is shown in Fig. 5. Assuming the droplet-to-particle mechanism, the data match the expected particle size distribution derived from droplet size measurements using an yttrium nitrate solution at 0.1 mol/L. The distribution peak given by the median particle size (22 nm) is in good agreement with the predicted median particle size (20 nm) from the droplet size data.

Fig. 5 Size distribution of particles synthesised using sub-micron droplets, 0.1 mol/L, T=1150 K, and predicted particle size distribution derived from the droplet size measurements.

Table 2 shows the mean particle size for the various precursor concentrations for T=1150 K. Note that only larger particles (>10 nm) were measured. The particle size now increases with precursor concentration in accord with these particles being formed via the droplet-to-particle mechanism. The results show that using sub-micron droplets composed of aqueous metal nitrate precursors and reducing the synthesis temperature it is possible to control the particle size using the one-droplet-to-one-particle route in the product size range of 10-100 nm.

Table 2

Measured and predicted mean particle sizes for sub-micron droplets, precursor concentrations 0.01-1 mol/L at T=1150 K.

Precursor concentration (mol/L)	Predicted mean particle size (nm)	Mean particle size (nm)
1	65.9	54.0
0.1	30.6	32.7
0.01	14.2	19.4

3.3 Luminescence characterisation of nanoparticles produced from sub-micron droplets

Figure 6 shows luminescence spectra of the various batches of synthesised particles. Figure 6a indicates that all three precursor concentrations for the low-temperature flame produce the bright red 611 nm emission line of $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$, corresponding to the $^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_2$ transition. The spectra of the flame-synthesised particles match well with the main emission lines of the commercial micron-sized powder at 587, 593, 599, 611 and 631 nm. These peaks are characteristic of the stable cubic phase of Y_2O_3 . Electron diffraction and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy data provided in the supplementary material also verify the crystallinity and purity of the particles.

Fig. 6 Normalised luminescence spectra of $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ nanoparticles synthesised using sub-micron droplets with: (a) precursor concentrations 0.01, 0.1 and 1 mol/L, flame temperature $T=1150$ K; (b) 0.1 mol/L, $T=2750$ K.

Dots denote the main emission peaks extracted from the measured spectra of commercial $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ powder. Arrows indicate the additional peaks from monoclinic $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$. 220 nm cw excitation with a 5 nm bandwidth was used.

Figure 6b shows the spectrum of particles produced in the high-temperature flame using sub-micron droplets. Additional peaks at 615 and 624 nm are visible, which are characteristic of monoclinic phase $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$. While elevated flame synthesis temperatures are known to favour the formation of the monoclinic phase [6, 11, 23], this may also be due to the particle size. Because of high surface curvature, nanoparticles are formed from the gas phase under increased internal pressure [23, 24], which may also explain the 615 nm emission peak for particles produced from 0.01 mol/L solutions in the low temperature flame.

3.4 Particle formation mechanisms: effect of synthesis temperature and droplet size

We then explore how the particle formation route as well as the final particle size and morphology depend on the initial droplet size and synthesis temperature. Figure 7 shows SEM images of nanoparticles prepared from 0.1 mol/L solutions using both sub-micron and micron-size droplets produced, respectively, using the microjet and ultrasonic atomisers. For sub-micron droplets, at the lowest temperature (1150 K), only particles with a diameter corresponding to a droplet-to-particle formation mechanism are observed. Upon increasing the flame temperature to 1400 K, 4-5 nm particles with a size consistent with formation from a gas-to-particle mechanism appear. For micron-size droplets, the morphologies of the larger particles are somewhat different, forming partially broken hollow and shell-like structures with diameters around 1-3 μm , as well as some 4-5 nm nanoparticles. At $T=2750$ K, sub-micron droplets seem to predominantly form nanoparticles from the gas-phase, whereas micron-size droplets produce a strongly bimodal distribution via both formation routes.

Fig. 7 SEM images of particles synthesised from 0.1 mol/L solutions using sub-micron (top) and micron-size (bottom) droplets in flames with different peak temperatures, with TEM insets.

To better understand these trends in relation to the early stages of the droplet-particle formation, a model was employed to determine the relative timescales of solvent evaporation [25] and solute diffusion. For a Biot number <0.1 and assuming conduction heat transfer only [26], the equation governing the droplet temperature T_d is given by [27]:

$$h_{fg}\dot{m}_v + c_{p,d}m_d \frac{dT_d}{dt} = 4\pi R_d k_g (T_g(t) - T_d) \quad (1)$$

where h_{fg} is the specific latent heat of solvent evaporation, $\dot{m}_v = 4\pi R_d D_v \frac{M}{\tilde{R}} (p_{v,s}/T_d - p_{v,g}/T_g(t))$ is the rate of solvent vapour mass transfer from the droplet, $c_{p,d}$ is the droplet specific heat capacity, m_d is the droplet mass, R_d is the droplet radius, and k_g the gas thermal conductivity. D_v is the vapour diffusion coefficient in the gas, M the molar mass, \tilde{R} the universal gas constant, and $p_{v,s}$ and $p_{v,g}$ are the partial pressures of vapour at the droplet surface and far away from the droplet, respectively. The carrier gas and droplets heat up as they approach the flame. To describe the temperature-time history we introduce a rate of gas temperature increase, hereafter referred to as the gas heating rate dT_g/dt . To determine the total droplet evaporation time τ_{evap} , the gas heating rate is used as an input to Eq. (1), which is solved in Matlab using a fifth-order Runge-Kutta method with initial temperatures $T_g=T_d=293$ K and the gas saturated with vapour, as determined by measuring the gas humidity at the exit of both atomisers. The characteristic time of bulk solute diffusion is calculated using $\tau_{diff} = R_D^2/D_s$, with D_s the solute diffusion coefficient, which for sodium nitrate is approximately 10^{-9} m²/s [28].

Firstly, we consider possible mechanisms for the formation of nanoparticles from the gas phase. Fig. 8 shows the dependence of water droplet lifetimes τ_{evap} on the gas heating rate for representative 200 nm and 3 μ m droplets. As the gas heating rate increases, the evaporation time decreases. The evaporation times are shorter for sub-micron droplets. The gas heating rates in the experiments were approximated with the centreline thermal gradient and the flow velocity. For the annular flames (Fig. 1e) the measured temperature increased from ambient to the peak temperature 30 mm downstream, yielding a relevant gas heating rate for the nanoparticles shown in Fig. 7 (T=1150 and 1400 K) of the order 10^4 K/s. For the closed flame (Fig. 1d), the gas heating rate was estimated using the adiabatic flame temperature and assuming a preheat region of the order 5 mm thick, resulting in $\sim 10^5$ K/s for the particles in Fig. 7 (T=2750 K). We hypothesise that during the extremely rapid drying the low-volatile nitrate precursor may be vaporised from the droplet surface directly into the gas-phase, whereupon nanoparticles form by nucleation and subsequent growth (see Fig. 9). Increasing the rate at which the droplet is heated will increase the vaporisation rate of both solvent and precursor, explaining the enhanced gas-phase formation of nanoparticles at higher synthesis temperatures as evidenced by Figs. 3 and 7.

Fig. 8 Model results for solvent evaporation and solute diffusion times for droplet diameters 200 nm and 3 μ m.

In general, at high synthesis temperatures it is also possible that metal compounds enter the gas phase in later stages of particle formation, after solvent evaporation is complete, say via vaporisation of precursor (metal salt) intermediates (shown in Fig. 9) and/or the final product. Regardless, both the above explanations of gas-phase nanoparticle formation are linked to surface area. That is, aerosols with greater surface area are expected to show enhanced gas-to-particle formation, a picture qualitatively supported by comparison of particles produced at $T=2750$ K from sub-micron and micron-size droplets, as shown in Fig. 7. More quantitatively, gas-to-particle formation proceeds according to the fraction of mass vaporised from the droplet/particle surface, which is inversely proportional to the droplet diameter squared. Here, the relevant parameter is the aerosol Sauter mean diameter D_{32} (the diameter of a droplet/particle with the same volume/surface area ratio as the entire aerosol), as measured using the laser diffraction instrument, and given in Table 3.

Table 3

Aerosol Sauter mean diameters D_{32} , and predicted and measured powder specific surface areas (SSA) produced using the two atomisers in the high temperature flame ($T=2750$ K) at precursor concentrations of 1 mol/L.

Atomiser	D_{32} (μ m)	Predicted powder SSA (m^2/g)	BET SSA (m^2/g)
microjet	3.5	1.2	45.3
ultrasound	5.5	0.8	12.4

For nanoparticles formed exclusively by the droplet-to-particle mechanism, D_{32} values permit calculation of the expected product powder specific surface area (SSA) shown in Table 3. The increase between the predicted and measured (BET-derived) SSA of product powders produced in the high-temperature flame ($T=2750$ K) is caused by gas-to-particle conversion, which produces particles with a SSA on the order 100 m^2/g . The key difference is the significantly larger surface area of the product powder produced by sub-micron droplets, which is in accordance with the gas-to-particle formation mechanisms proposed above. These explanations agree with the results of studies that synthesised $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ [7] and also NiO [17, 29] nanoparticles with a size consistent with a gas-to-particle formation mechanism, using aqueous nitrate micron-size solution droplets in a spray pyrolysis reactor at 0.01-0.05 bar. At low pressures the fraction of vaporised mass increases because the mass transfer of vapour from the droplet/particle surface is faster. Using smaller droplets also increases the vaporised mass fraction.

Secondly, formation of hollow particles is considered. A gas heating rate at which the droplet evaporation becomes slower than solute diffusion within the droplet can be defined, and as shown in Fig. 8 this value is lower for 3 μm droplets (5×10^4 K/s) than for 200 nm droplets (10^7 K/s). For larger droplets the evaporation is completed at a higher gas/droplet temperature because the evaporation time is longer. Therefore the vapour pressure at the droplet surface over the course of the droplet lifetime is on average higher. This explains why, for a given gas heating rate, as the droplet size increases, the evaporation time decreases relative to the solute diffusion time. Note that constant temperature analyses do not reveal this difference between droplet sizes [16, 27, 30]. For reference, for all experimental conditions the final gas temperatures at which the droplets are completely evaporated are significantly lower than the peak flame temperatures.

For sub-micron droplets, Fig. 8 suggests that solvent evaporation proceeds more slowly than solute diffusion ($\tau_{\text{evap}} \gg \tau_{\text{diff}}$), leading to volume precipitation and dense polycrystalline features of the particles shown in Fig. 4. This is not so for droplets produced by the ultrasonic atomiser, where at a heating rate of 10^4 K/s the model predicts that the two processes are in competition ($\tau_{\text{evap}} \sim \tau_{\text{diff}}$). The SEM images of Fig. 7 ($T=1150$ and 1400 K) shows large particles several microns in diameter, which the TEM (inset) reveals to be hollow. It appears as though as the particle size decreases, the probability it will have a solid core seems to increase. This can be understood by considering the droplet size distribution of Fig. 2 together with the timescale analysis of Fig. 8,

where smaller droplets among the distribution would be more likely to precipitate homogeneously. At *lower* heating rates, particles produced by micron-size droplets will be dense [9]. At *higher* heating rates, Fig. 8 shows that the rate of solvent evaporation exceeds that of solute diffusion, a case corresponding to the particles synthesised from micron-size droplets at $T=2750$ K as shown in Fig. 7. This indicates that when introducing micron-sized aqueous metal nitrate solution droplets into flames of this kind, the precursor always starts to precipitate on the droplet surface, forming a shell early on. A mechanism following a sequence of precursor melting and decomposition then proceeds. Following the route shown in Fig. 9, particle shrinkage and coalescence take place under conditions of elevated temperature [31], finally leading to dense product particles (see Fig. 7 inset). Guo et al. synthesised hollow $Y_2O_3:Eu$ in H_2 /air flames, but dense spherical $Y_2O_3:Eu$ in higher temperature H_2/O_2 flames [12]. Together, these results suggest it may be necessary to approach or exceed the melting temperature of Y_2O_3 (2700 K [32]) to produce dense product particles, if hollow particles were formed initially. This droplet size-dependent shell formation process could also couple to the gas-to-particle nanoparticle formation route via micro-explosion phenomena previously observed in single droplet experiments, e.g. ref. [20]. The findings may also offer an additional explanation (besides that of high-temperature phase equilibrium) for the formation of particles with crystal or compositional heterogeneity, e.g. core-shell particles [33]. Compositional gradients established by early surface precipitation could persist in the product particles.

Fig. 9. Particle formation routes

4. Conclusions

Synthesis of sub-100 nm luminescent $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ nanoparticles was successfully conducted in non-premixed flames, using a new microjet atomisation technology producing sub-micron aerosol droplets. Two different particle formation mechanisms, droplet-to-particle and gas-to-particle, and their dependence on synthesis temperature and aerosol droplet size were investigated by comparing the microjet atomiser with the micron-size droplets of conventional ultrasonic atomisation. The main findings are:

- (1) At low synthesis temperatures of 1150 K the sub-micron droplet flame synthesis method is able to produce dense polycrystalline nanoparticles from aqueous metal nitrate solutions via a direct droplet-to-particle mechanism. The particle size can be efficiently controlled in the range $\sim 10\text{-}100$ nm using precursor concentrations $\sim 0.01\text{-}1$ mol/L. The luminescence of the $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ particles indicate the stable cubic phase.
- (2) At high flame temperatures (~ 2750 K), nanoparticles with a size $\sim 4\text{-}5$ nm are formed via a gas-to-particle mechanism. Surface area measurements of the product powder show that sub-micron droplets form an increased fraction of nanoparticles from the gas-phase compared with micron-size droplets, possibly caused by enhanced vaporisation of precursor directly into the gas-phase during solvent evaporation. Future investigations will aim to isolate this phenomenon from other possible mechanisms, e.g. intermediate/product vaporisation, and target extreme gas heating rates relevant to other synthesis processes e.g. flame spray pyrolysis.
- (3) Experiments and modelling indicate that sub-micron droplets are more robust in that they form homogenous dense particles by a direct droplet-to-particle route even at high rates of gas temperature increase (10^4 K/s), because solute diffusion within the droplet proceeds faster than droplet evaporation. For the same conditions, micron-size droplets form hollow/broken particles and high peak temperatures near the product melting point (>2700 K) are subsequently required to promote dense particle formation.

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Fig.1 Experimental setup: atomiser sketches (a,b), synthesis burner (c), and flame photographs (d,e).

Fig. 2 Water droplet size distributions for microjet and ultrasonic atomisers.

Fig. 3 SEM image of $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ nanoparticles produced using sub-micron 1 mol/L solution droplets at a flame temperature $T=2750$ K, with TEM inset.

Fig. 4 TEM images of $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ nanoparticles produced using sub-micron droplets in a lower temperature flame $T=1150$ K.

Fig. 5 Size distribution of particles synthesised using sub-micron droplets, 0.1 mol/L, $T=1150$ K, and predicted particle size distribution derived from the droplet size measurements.

Fig. 6 Normalised luminescence spectra of $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ nanoparticles synthesised using sub-micron droplets with: (a) precursor concentrations 0.01, 0.1 and 1 mol/L, flame temperature $T=1150$ K; (b) 0.1 mol/L, $T=2750$ K. Dots denote the main emission peaks extracted from the measured spectra of commercial $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ powder. Arrows indicate the additional peaks from monoclinic $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$. 220 nm cw excitation with a 5 nm bandwidth was used.

Fig. 7 SEM images of particles synthesised from 0.1 mol/L solutions using sub-micron (top) and micron-size (bottom) droplets in flames with different peak temperatures, with TEM insets.

Fig. 8 Model results for solvent evaporation and solute diffusion times for droplet diameters 200 nm and 3 μm .

Fig. 9. Particle formation routes

List of tables

Table 1

Measured mean particle sizes for precursor concentrations 0.01-1 mol/L at T=2750 K.

Precursor concentration (mol/L)	Mean primary particle size (nm)
0.01	3.8
0.1	3.7
1	5.6

Table 2

Measured and predicted mean particle sizes for sub-micron droplets, precursor concentrations 0.01-1 mol/L at T=1150 K.

Precursor concentration (mol/L)	Predicted mean particle size (nm)	Mean particle size (nm)
1	65.9	54.0
0.1	30.6	32.7
0.01	14.2	19.4

Table 3

Aerosol Sauter mean diameters D_{32} , and predicted and measured powder specific surface areas (SSA) produced using the two atomisers in the high temperature flame (T=2750 K) at precursor concentrations of 1 mol/L.

Atomiser	D_{32} (μm)	Predicted powder SSA (m^2/g)	BET SSA (m^2/g)
microjet	3.5	1.2	45.3
ultrasound	5.5	0.8	12.4

List of supplemental files

Supplementary material - Micro-aerosol flame synthesis C Abram - ProcI revisions.docx